

Dynamic Relationship between Environmental Disclosure, Financial Report Quality and Financial Performance of Companies

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Abstract

The study is set to identify the dynamic relationship among environmental disclosure, financial report quality and financial performance of companies. The research employed the ex-post facto research design. The population of the study consist of all the 43 manufacturing companies on the Nigerian stock exchange. The study used secondary data which was extracted from the annual reports and account of the manufacturing companies for the years covered by the study. The multiple regression technique was used to analysed data. The results showed that Environmental Disclosure (EDI) plays a crucial role in influencing Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ), which in turn can have a positive effect on financial performance (ROA) of the companies. Based on the above findings, this study concludes that that Environmental Disclosure (EDI) largely operates on a self-deterministic basis, indicating that improvements in sustainability practices are primarily driven by internal corporate policies as well as Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) positively influenced by environmental disclosure, indicating that firms committed to transparency in environmental practices tend to enhance their overall reporting quality. The study therefore recommended that companies should continue to focus on improving the quality of their financial reporting, as it directly impacts their profitability and market valuation. In addition, companies, especially those with strong financial performance, should allocate resources toward improving the quality and depth of their sustainability reporting.

Keywords: Companies, Environmental disclosure, Financial report quality, Financial performance, Sustainability practices.

Word Count: 220

Introduction

Across several scholarly discourses, financial performance has been discussed as a critical priority in all economic decision making relating to public and private companies to recognize the difficult location and areas. It is based on many decisions such as executive compensation, stock prices, stock risk, decision related to investment and many other cases (Olasupo & Akinselure, 2017). The performance of companies depends on administrative decisions which are implemented within the company and is proven by the ability of managers to manage a business and maximize the owner's

wealth. In more extensive sense, it refers to the degree to which financial objective being or has been accomplished. It is the process of measuring company's policies and operation in monetary terms. It is used to measure company's overall financial health over a given period of time. Financial performance of a firm is reflected in its corporate success. It involves the use of organization assets to generate revenue. Financial performance enables management to give account of their stewardship to shareholders on firm profitability, value and firm growth (Charles & John-Akamelu, 2017; Oyedokun, Umoh, Haruna, & Zakari, 2019).

The nature of a company activities defines the risk attached to such business and risk constitute a significant factor in the profitability of the firm's operation. Higher financial risks constitute enormous treats to firm's profitability, though they are likely to attract huge amount of profits. With the aids of the financial performance, stakeholders were able and thus encourage them to make decision, Analysing financial ratios during a specific time is the best way to assess the financial performance of companies (Wen & Zhou, 2017; Dauda, Ojo, Oyedokun, & Ajayi-Owoeye, 2018).

Environmentally sensitive manufacturing companies are whose operations have significant influence on their environment. They are essentially manufacturing company. A vivid understanding of environmental disclosure is critical for the company's stakeholders, such as management, investor, creditors, accountants and auditors. Nigerian companies have been under increasingly pressure to disclose information on their environmental practices for years. Environmental disclosure is about company's disclosing information in respect of their environmental management practices. The proposition is that disclosing information regarding a company's environmental practices may be beneficial to the company's reputation and by extension help to improve the company's financial performance (Olasupo & Akinselure, 2017; Yahaya, Oyedokun, & Aruwa, 2019). Environmental issues have increasingly drawn the attention of the world at different levels, and corporate social and environmental responsibility has become a major contemporary focus of business, government and community attention globally. As a result, interest in corporate disclosure of environmental information has grown in recent years. However, attention on environmental disclosure has been confined to the companies of developed countries, while the developing countries suffer from environmental disclosure practice in corporations. Among the largest consumers of natural and social resources, business organizations have come under increased pressure to justify the nature and scale of their consumption (Ahmed, Waseer, Hussain & Ammara, 2018; Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020).

It is well recognized that environmental performance of the manufacturing companies on the natural environment are very high. In addition to the environmental issues that affects that result from normal operation of the manufacturing company's activities, the effects maybe the result of occasional events. During the last four decades, the manufacturing companies have witnessed several critical environmental incidents. The occurrence of environmental incidents as a result of activities of manufacturing companies have contributed to the increase of environmental awareness and put the accounting sector under societal pressure to reduce its impact on the environment (Yahaya, 2018; Ojo, Oyedokun, & Fodio, 2020). However, the increase has largely influenced business to engage in environmental management and practice including environmental reporting, The obvious difference between environmental information disclosure and financial

information disclosure lies in that financial information is mandatory disclosure items which have more obvious relationship with financial performance, while environmental information is largely voluntary disclosure items which have great uncertainty about the relationship with financial performance, Disclosures are cornerstone of transparency that can decrease corruption and mismanagement (Udo, 2019).

There is the increased expectation of all companies to be more transparent in how they threat the environment, handle their corporate governance issues, treat their employees and communities, corporations have become more sensitive to issues and stakeholder concerns, and are striving to become better corporate citizens. Whether the motivation is concern for society and environment, government regulation, stakeholder pressures or economic profit, the result is that managers must make significant changes to manage their social, economic and environmental impact more effectively. This study aims to identify the dynamic relationship among environmental disclosure, financial report quality and financial performance of companies.

Literature Review

Environmental Disclosure

Environmental accounting disclosure rankings are significant indicators of the organisational effectiveness of the company, signalling to the public the viability and social responsiveness of the company, creating a favourable economic, social and political situation for businesses, creating a better reputation, improving access to capital markets and attracting investors. Favourable environmental accounting disclosure is essentially a signal that affects the behaviour of the corporate audiences and /or stakeholders of the same company and the expectations of the importance of earnings to the determination of stock returns (Olasupo & Akinselure, 2017; Oyedokun, Yunusa, & Adeyemo, 2018).

According to Solikhah, Wahyudin, Yulianto and Fathudin (2018) the primary purpose of environmental disclosure is to examine and incorporate in the firm annual reports issues that bother on environmental hazard that are not taken cognizance of in traditional or conventional accounting function that stakeholders can use for decision making. Disclosure of corporate environmental activities stressed the necessity for a close monitoring of natural resources and the corporation's harmful effect on the society it operate. Environmental effects caused by activities of firms especially those in the manufacturing, oil and gas and banking include pollutions like noise, waste, hazardous emission, spillages, degradation. In recent years, then, a belief has arisen in businesses and in society that reporting has a wider role than that expressed in the traditional 'stockholder/shareholder' perspective.

Importantly, one need not hold to the 'deep green' end of the argument to hold these views: there are strategic reasons why a wider view of accountability may be held and, accordingly, why initiatives such as environmental reporting may be supported; environmental consequences of an organisation's inputs and outputs. Inputs include the measurement of key environmental resources

such as energy, water, inventories (especially if any of these are scarce or threatened), land use, etc. Outputs include the efficiency of internal processes (possibly including a ‘mass balance’ or ‘yield’ calculation) and the impact of outputs. These might include the proportion of product recyclability, tones of carbon or other gases produced by company activities, any waste or pollution (Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017).

These measures can apply directly (narrowly) or indirectly (more broadly). A direct environmental accounting measures those within the reporting entity whereas an indirect measure will also report on the forward and backward supply chains which the company has incurred in bringing the products from their origins to the market. For example, a company can directly report on the environmental impact of its own company: its branches and main office. But to produce a full environmental report, a company would also need to include the environmental consequences of those activities it facilitates through its business loans. Where a company claims to report on its environmental impacts, it rarely includes these indirect measures because it is hard to measure environmental impacts outside the reporting company and there is a dispute about whether such measures should be included in the company’s report (the company may say it is for the other company to report on its own impacts) (Charles & John-Akamelu, 2017).

A research shows that more and more organizations decide to report environmental information to their stakeholders. In the early 1990s, concluded that, despite the majority of the companies in France, Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden and Switzerland disclose environmental information; the level of this information is low. Nevertheless, a study performed to the 250 largest Fortune 500 companies (this data represents companies from France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, South Korea, Switzerland, the UK and the US) during the years 1998 to 2001, concluded that environmental reporting has increased considerably within those countries. The author also concluded that environmental reporting is applied more in the industrial sectors than in the financial sectors. The level of environmental disclosure is also depending on country specific legislation and the reporting culture of the country. The companies make more environmental disclosures in such regulated countries, especially in the USA, Canada and the UK either because environmental reporting is mandatory or because society or stakeholders demand reporting (Wen & Zhou, 2017). Besides the mandatory requirements to disclose environmental information, there are a variety of reasons why organizations decide to, voluntarily, disclose this information.

Determinants of Environmental Disclosure

The environmental reporting or sometimes known as “Green reporting” is one of the voluntary social reporting included the financial statements (Udo, 2019). The main determinant of environmental reporting includes:

Company Size

A positive association between size and voluntary social responsibility disclosure. In support of the positive relation that firstly, the cost of accounting and generating certain information is greater for small firms than large firms. Small companies may not be able to afford such costs from their resources base. Larger companies might have sufficient resources to afford the cost of producing information for the user of the annual report. Secondly, it believes that agency costs are higher for large companies because shareholders are widespread and, in that way, disclosing more information reduce the potential agency cost. Additionally, these firms might publish more information in their reports to supply information relevant to different users (Udo, 2016).

Also, large companies may tend to disclose more information than smaller companies in their annual reports due to their competitive cost advantage. Hence, small companies disclose less information than large companies suggest those firms which are more visible in the public eyes are likely to voluntarily disclose information to enhance their corporate reputations (Suttipun, 2017).

Financial Leverage

Agency theory to assert the political transfers of wealth from bondholders to shareholders can take place in highly leverage firms. The proportion of outside capital tends to be higher for large firms as the potential benefits of voluntary disclosure increase with shareholder debt holder-manager conflicts (Eluyela & Ilogho, 2016).

Profitability

More profitable firms are more likely to disclose more while less profitable firms tend to be more secretive. Profitable firms may be more inclined to disclose more information in order to screen themselves from less profitable firms. However, there is certain ambiguity in theoretical and empirical studies regarding the sign of profitability in relation to disclosure and therefore the relationship between disclosure and profitability is non-monotonic. This is because less profitable firms may disclose more information to explain the reasons for the negative performance and reassure the market about future growth. Companies also disclose bad news at an early opportunity in order to mitigate the risk of legal liability, severe devaluation of share capital and loss reputation (Okwuosa and Amaeshi, 2017).

Effective Tax Rates

Another measure of political visibility is the effective tax. The taxation system provides the most direct means by which wealth transfer can be made from companies to the government. Income tax can be reviewed as one of the components of political cost borne by a company. This suggests that a company that is liable to pay relatively higher levels of taxation may be seen to be presently subject to high levels of political cost. A company which is subjected to a high taxation burden

may be motivated to employ techniques that reduce these costs. This shows that companies with higher effective tax rates are more likely to disclose more voluntary information than companies with lower effective tax rates an effort to reduce political cost (Atale & Otuya, 2018).

Industrial Membership

Each industry has different characteristics from each other, which may relate to competition growth and risk and specific culture to historical factors. These may provide scope of differential disclosure. Limitation and tradition can ensure that new entrants to an industry are likely to follow accounting methods used by industry leaders. Moreover, different industries have different property cost, which gives incentive for companies belonging to the same industry to disclose more or less information than companies belonging to another industry (Arowoshegbe, Uniamikogbo & Atu, 2017)

Audit Firm

Auditors play a major role in opportunities behaviors by agents, thereby reducing the agency cost born by principles and agents. Auditors incur cost from entering contracts with an audit and so will influence clients to disclose so much information as possible in their annual reports. Auditors with high reputations are less to be associated with clients to disclose low level of information in their published annual reports (IFAC, 2016)

Profitability

The relationship between profitability and environmental disclosure is mixed. Profitability is significant and positively associated with environmental disclosure. There is no significant association exists between profitability and its level of environmental disclosure. If the company achieves a high margin of profit the managerial groups are motivated to disclose more information in order to show off a good reputation to the customers, shareholders, investors and other stakeholders. On the other hand, if the profitability is low or the company suffers losses, they may disclose less information in order to cover the reasons for such losses or declining profits. Profitability is measured as return on revenues, return on total assets and return on equity (Nor, Bahari, Adnan, Qamaral, Kamal & Ali, 2016).

Corporate Environmental Disclosure

Corporate environmental disclosure is the process by which a corporation communicates information regarding the range of its environmental activities to a variety of stakeholders including employees, local communities, shareholders, costumers, government and environmental groups. Really, the objective of financial reporting is to provide information which should be comprehensible to those who have a reasonable understanding of business and economic activities and are willing to study the information with reasonable diligence. Against this backdrop,

corporate reports which disclose the performance and position of companies without significant environmental cost disclosure will be showing a distorted view of the business (Etim & Effiong, 2021). Corporate environmental disclosure serves many different purposes for different stakeholders, which include the following: it permits investors to harness the power of the capital markets to promote and ensure environmentally-superior business practices; it empowers people with the information they need to hold on corporation's accountable and invites shareholders more fully into the process of corporate goal setting; it allows companies and their stakeholders to measure companies adherence to the standards set forth in their statements of environmental principle, and their various goals and objectives; it will allow society to understand the false implications of corporate activity thereby to design where sustainable local and global systems; as an internal driver of change, it helps illuminate weaknesses and opportunities and set new goals (Amaechi & Chinedu, 2017).

Financial Reporting Quality

Financial reporting provides a variety of information and stakeholders are increasingly paying more attention to environmental issues related to financial performance. Thus, plenty of researchers have focused on the relationship between financial performance and environmental disclosure and have reported mixed results. A linkage between environmental management practices and improved future financial performance and discover a significant positive financial return for strong environmental management while significant negative financial returns for weak environmental management. Firms with a higher pollution propensity and greater media coverage of their environmental performance are more likely to disclose general environmental information in Canadian manufacturing firms (Fasua & Osifo, 2020). There is a significant positive relationship between environmental management practices and measures of firm performance.

Financial reporting quality is the exact manner in which it shows information regard business activity and its anticipated cash flow, intending to inform the shareholder about a company's operations. Financial reporting quality as the faithfulness of information conveyed in the financial reporting process. Financial reporting is also defined as the degree to which financial statements provide us with information that is fair and authentic about the financial position and performance of an enterprise (Mohammed, 2018). It can be deduced from the above definition that for a financial statement to be regarded as possessing a high-quality attribute, it must be able to provide genuine authentic information about the economic performance of the firm.

Financial reporting is defined as the faithfulness of information conveyed in both the financial and non-financial reporting process. The financial statement of firms at the end of a financial year should have some element of truth in it. This is termed quality to increase the confidence of users. The firm's economic performance (measured by profitability) is important in the decision to be made in environmental disclosure.

The main focus of financial reporting is to provide high-quality financial information concerning economic entities which are considered useful for economic decision making. Providing high quality financial information is important because it will positively influence users of accounting information such as investors, capital providers and other stakeholders in making investment, credit, and similar resource allocation decisions thereby enhancing overall stock market efficiency (Zamil & Hassan 2019).

Financial Performance

Financial performance of a firm is reflected in its corporate success. According to Nguyen and Tran (2019), It involves the use of organization assets to generate revenue. Financial performance enables management to give account of their stewardship to shareholders on firm profitability, value and firm growth. Financial performance is the extent to which organization objectives and policies have been achieved in monetary term. Company is assumed to be performing if it is able to meet its obligations as at when due. In accounting literature, financial performance of firms has been measured as firm growth, size of the firm, firm's profitability or market share. Firm's size is often measured as Total Assets; profitability as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Net Profit Margin, Earnings Per Share, Gross Profit Margin or Profit After Tax.

Financial performance is commonly used as an indicator of a firm's financial health over a given period of time. The financial performance of a firm can be defined or measured in various different ways including profitability, gauge return, market share growth, return on investment, return on equity and liquidity. Financial performance was measured by the development of revenues and profits (Alok, Nikhil & Bhagaban, 2018). Revenue development can be seen as a growth indicator of the firm and also as a competitive strategy for consecutive firms. A firm can, by being environmentally sustainable, differentiate its products and thus increase its revenue. Similarly, a firm can save costs on resources, regulatory costs, capital and labour and therewith increase its profits (Bednárová, Klimko & Rievajová, 2019). In this study, financial performance will be measured by, Net Profit Margin (NPM), Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

Environmental Disclosure, Financial Reporting Quality and Financial Performance

The link between the concept of Environmental Disclosure and Concept of Financial Performance connotes incorporation or non-incorporation of the environmental information in the annual reports of the companies whose activities are prone to causing environmental degradations which in turn informs the decisions of the stakeholders either positively or negatively (George-Silviu & Melinda-Timea, 2015). The study concluded that firms which produce environmental disclosure have better financial performance than those that do not. In addition, US firms, and used the value of net income/total assets as their performance proxy. They found that high performance firms had higher disclosure of environmental policies and/or descriptions of environmental commitment compared to poor performing firms (Gao & Zhang, 2019).

Environmental disclosure and financial reporting quality, as independent variables, may also interact to influence financial performance in manufacturing companies. High-quality financial reporting will enhance the credibility and usefulness of environmental disclosures, as stakeholders are more likely to depend mostly and act upon environmental information that is supported by accurate and reliable financial data comprehensive environmental disclosures can complement financial reporting by providing a more realistic view of a company's long-term sustainability and risk profile, potentially leading to improved financial performance.

The combined effect of environmental disclosure and financial reporting quality on financial performance is actually significant in manufacturing companies. These firms are often subject to stringent environmental regulations and intense public scrutiny due to their substantial environmental impact. Consequently, both comprehensive environmental disclosures and high-quality financial reporting are critical tools for maintaining legitimacy, managing risks, and fostering trust among stakeholders, which enhance financial performance of Companies at the long run

Theoretical Review

This study employed Social Contract Theory. The social contract theory is developed on the proposition that there exists a contract between business and wider society, whereby business agrees to perform various societal desired actions in return for approval of its objectives, other rewards and its ultimate survival (Pamela & Christopher, n.d).

For the furtherance of this study, the researcher will limit its conceptual framework to the Stakeholder's theory. Numerous views about Stakeholder's theory that are presented in the literature through key distinction can be drawn between the tenets of stakeholder theory and conventional input-output model of the firm which see firms as converting investors, supplier and employee into customers output (Deegan & Jeffrey, 2016). In contrast, stakeholder theory argues that every legitimate person or group participating in the activities of a firm does so to obtain benefit and that the priority of the interest of all legitimate stakeholders is not self-evident.

There are four central theses related to stakeholder theory: First, stakeholder theory is descriptive in that it offers a model of the corporation. Stakeholders' theory is instrumental in offering a framework of investigating the links between conventional firm performance and the practice of stakeholder management. Although stakeholder theory is descriptive and instrumental it is more fundamentally normative. Third, Stakeholders are identified by their interest and all stakeholder interests are considered to be intrinsically valuable. Finally, Stakeholder theory is managerial, in that it recommends attitudes, structure and practices and require simultaneous attention is given to the interest of all legitimate stakeholders. Hence, the theory proposes that firms' performance is dependent on the relationship between the firms and all stakeholders (Elijido-Ten, 2016).

Empirical Review

Che Ahmad, Osazuwa and Mgbame (2015) investigated environmental accounting and firm profitability in Nigeria using ordinary least square regression (OLS). With a sample of 50 listed companies and a cross-sectional research design, data were obtained from annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms. The research evidence showed that a significant relationship exist between environmental accounting and firm's profitability. However, the study revealed a negative relationship when moderated by firm size.

Alhassan and Anwural Islam (2019) examined the link between environmental costs accounting and reporting of firm financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Proxied by cost of environmental remediation and pollution control, cost of environmental laws compliance and penalty, donations and charitable contributions. It was established that environmental performance influence business value positively. Data obtained from five (5) sampled oil and gas firms was analysed using multiple regression with a panel data model. The study also revealed that, environmental accounting provides organisation's an opportunity to reduce environmental and social costs and improve their performance.

Nguyen and Tran (2019) assessed the relationship between disclosure levels of environmental accounting information and financial performance. Data were collected from the firms listed in Vietnam Stock Exchange from 2013 to 2017, including the firms disclosed and the ones did not disclose the environmental accounting information. The study used two regression models to investigate the relationship between environmental accounting information and return on assets. The results indicated that there was a close relationship between disclosure level of environmental accounting information and financial performance. In addition, there was a difference in terms of financial performance between the firms that did not disclose environmental accounting information and the ones that disclosed the environmental accounting information.

Methodology

The ex-post facto research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consisted of all the 43 manufacturing Companies on the Nigerian stock exchange. Data was gathered using content analysis. The study employs secondary data which was extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the manufacturing companies for the years covered by the study. Data was analysed using multiple regression techniques.

Presentation of Data

Is there any dynamic relationship among environmental disclosure, financial report quality and financial performance of companies?

The Dynamic Relationships among Environmental Disclosure, Financial Reporting Quality, and Financial Performance

This analysis delves into the dynamic relationships among Environmental Disclosure (EDI), Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ), and Return on Assets (ROA) by examining variance decomposition and impulse response as obtained from the VAR model. Variance decomposition captures how much of the forecast error variance of each variable can be attributed to shocks in the other variables over time. This approach reveals the interdependencies among these variables and helps us understand their influence on each other.

Variance Decomposition of Environmental Disclosure (EDI)

Period 1: At the initial stage, EDI is entirely self-explanatory, with 100% of its variance accounted for by its own shocks. This indicates that environmental disclosure at this point is driven solely by internal factors within the firm, with no immediate influence from financial reporting quality (FRQ) or return on assets (ROA).

Periods 2 to 10: Over the subsequent periods, the contributions from FRQ and ROA to the variance in EDI gradually increase but remain extremely small (less than 0.1%). In Period 2 specifically, FRQ accounts for 0.012992% of EDI's variance, while ROA contributes 0.007120%. This trend continues, with small increases in their contributions over time. By Period 10, the contributions from FRQ and ROA are 0.008458% and 0.086799%, respectively. This slight increase suggests a growing acknowledgment of the role that financial reporting and performance metrics may play in shaping environmental disclosures, albeit their influence remains minimal relative to the self-deterministic nature of EDI.

Variance Decomposition of Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ)

Period 1: At the outset, 79.18% of the variance in FRQ is attributed to its own shocks, while 20.82% is explained by EDI. This suggests that financial reporting quality is substantially influenced by its historical performance, with a significant acknowledgment of the role that environmental disclosure plays in shaping it.

Periods 2 to 10: Over time, the proportion of variance explained by EDI increases steadily. In Period 10, EDI accounts for 28.36% of the variance in FRQ, indicating that as firms improve their environmental disclosures, they also tend to enhance the quality of their financial reporting. The proportion of variance explained by FRQ itself declines, suggesting that as firms rely more on EDI

for transparency, the relative importance of historical FRQ diminishes. The small contributions from ROA (hovering around 0.004%) indicate that financial performance has a negligible direct impact on financial reporting quality compared to the effects of EDI.

Variance Decomposition of Return on Assets (ROA)

Period 1: In the initial period, 99.92% of the variance in ROA is explained by its shocks. Contributions from EDI and FRQ are negligible at 0.030114% and 0.045632%, respectively. This reflects that ROA is predominantly driven by its historical performance at this early stage.

Periods 2 to 10: As time progresses, the contributions from EDI and FRQ to the variance in ROA gradually increase. For instance, by Period 10, EDI contributes 0.838775%, and FRQ contributes 1.891247% to the variance in ROA. However, despite this gradual increase, ROA remains predominantly influenced by its own past values, which continue to account for around 97% of its variance throughout the observed periods. This indicates that while EDI and FRQ do have some influence on financial performance, their impacts are relatively minor compared to the direct effects of historical ROA.

It was obvious that environmental disclosure exhibits a strong self-deterministic nature, with minimal influence from FRQ and ROA. This implies that improvements in environmental disclosure practices primarily arise from internal company initiatives rather than external financial reporting standards or performance metrics. Moreover, over time, the variance decomposition results reveal that the influence of environmental disclosure on financial reporting quality grows, suggesting that firms that are more transparent about their environmental impact tend to improve their financial reporting practices.

Furthermore, return on assets is predominantly influenced by its historical performance, with only minor contributions from EDI and FRQ. This suggests that while EDI and FRQ may encourage better financial performance, the immediate effect of past performance remains the strongest predictor.

Table 1: Variance Decomposition

Variance Decomposition of EDI:				
Period	S.E.	EDI	FRQ	ROA
1	0.268008	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.363104	99.97989	0.012992	0.007120
3	0.430143	99.94280	0.014172	0.043024
4	0.481744	99.92630	0.013334	0.060364

5	0.523276	99.91852	0.011974	0.069504
6	0.557540	99.91384	0.010684	0.075476
7	0.586263	99.91067	0.009663	0.079669
8	0.610615	99.90831	0.008962	0.082724
9	0.631434	99.90640	0.008571	0.085024
10	0.649345	99.90474	0.008458	0.086799

Variance Decomposition of FRQ:

Period	S.E.	EDI	FRQ	ROA
1	0.190403	20.82269	79.17731	0.000000
2	0.265197	22.56830	77.42761	0.004098
3	0.313793	23.63762	76.35794	0.004445
4	0.348866	24.52419	75.47123	0.004580
5	0.375384	25.30785	74.68780	0.004353
6	0.395998	26.02089	73.97501	0.004102
7	0.412322	26.67727	73.31886	0.003870
8	0.425423	27.28376	72.71257	0.003668
9	0.436044	27.84441	72.15210	0.003499
10	0.444724	28.36208	71.63456	0.003364

Variance Decomposition of ROA:

Period	S.E.	EDI	FRQ	ROA
1	0.586263	0.030114	0.045632	99.92425
2	0.589689	0.563749	0.664965	98.77129
3	0.591226	0.616960	0.978156	98.40488
4	0.592025	0.655369	1.205255	98.13938

5	0.592710	0.695913	1.390740	97.91335
6	0.593271	0.732159	1.539737	97.72810
7	0.593729	0.763934	1.658754	97.57731
8	0.594105	0.791996	1.753959	97.45405
9	0.594413	0.816817	1.830186	97.35300
10	0.594667	0.838775	1.891247	97.26998
Cholesky Ordering: EDI FRQ ROA				

Impulse Response Analysis:

Response of EDI to Innovations in FRQ and ROA: The response of Environmental Disclosure (EDI) to innovations in both FRQ and ROA indicates a positive trend over time, suggesting that improvements in financial reporting quality and financial performance can lead to enhanced environmental disclosures by firms. Although the initial response may be modest, it grows over several periods, implying that companies may gradually increase their transparency about environmental practices as they strengthen their financial performance and reporting standards.

Response of FRQ to Innovations in EDI and ROA:

The Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) shows a positive reaction to innovations in both EDI and ROA. This suggests that companies that are more transparent about their environmental impact tend to also exhibit higher-quality financial reporting. Additionally, firms with better financial performance (measured by ROA) tend to improve their financial reporting practices over time. This positive dynamic may reflect the importance of maintaining high standards of financial reporting as companies become more environmentally responsible and improve their financial health.

Response of ROA to Innovations in EDI and FRQ:

Return on Assets (ROA) responds positively to innovations in both EDI and FRQ. The results suggest that firms that improve their environmental disclosure and financial reporting practices also experience better financial performance over time. The relationship between environmental transparency and financial performance is likely driven by enhanced investor confidence and market valuation, as firms with better disclosure practices are perceived as lower-risk and more sustainable investments.

Response to Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations

Discussion of Findings

The Dynamic Relationships. Among Environmental Disclosure, Financial Reporting Quality, and Financial Performance

This analysis delves into the intricate relationships among Environmental Disclosure (EDI), Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ), and Return on Assets (ROA) through variance decomposition and impulse response analysis. By employing a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model, the study uncovers how shocks in one variable affect the others over time, revealing a dynamic interplay that informs corporate governance, reporting practices, and financial performance. The result shows that environmental Disclosure (EDI) largely operates on a self-deterministic basis, indicating that improvements in sustainability practices are primarily driven by internal corporate policies. Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) is positively influenced by environmental disclosure, indicating that firms committed to transparency in environmental practices tend to enhance their overall reporting quality. Return on Assets (ROA) is predominantly influenced by its historical values, with only minor contributions from EDI and FRQ, suggesting that while environmental transparency can enhance financial performance, historical performance remains the strongest predictor. The analysis reveals that Environmental Disclosure (EDI) plays a crucial role in influencing Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ), which in turn can have a positive effect on financial performance (ROA). Firms that prioritize environmental transparency are likely to benefit from improved financial reporting practices and, consequently, better financial performance. These findings underscore the importance of integrating environmental initiatives within corporate governance frameworks to foster long-term sustainability and enhance financial outcomes.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study investigated the relationship between financial reporting quality and financial performance. The study establishes a positive relationship between financial reporting quality (FRQ) and companies' performance, demonstrating that higher-quality financial reporting enhances both profitability (ROA) and market valuation (Tobin's Q). This underscores the importance of transparency in improving investor confidence and reducing information asymmetry. Additionally, while leverage boosts market value, its impact on operational efficiency remains limited, indicating the need for careful debt management. It was evidenced that the findings indicate that companies that prioritize environmental transparency and high-quality financial reporting are better positioned to enhance their financial performance. The findings was able to establish the dynamic relationships between financial reporting quality and financial performance in manufacturing companies.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made to enhance financial reporting quality and improve financial performance within the Nigerian manufacturing sector:

- i. Companies, especially those with strong financial performance, should allocate resources toward improving the quality and depth of their sustainability reporting.
- ii. Companies should continue to focus on improving the quality of their financial reporting, as it directly impacts their profitability and market valuation.
- iii. Companies with high leverage should carefully manage their debt levels while maintaining a focus on sustainability.

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